

Wavefunction and the Identity of a Momentum State in a Quantum Bound State

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An unusual feature of bound state quantum mechanics is that there is a spatial density (or probability to be at $x = P(x)$), just as in classical statistical mechanics, but also a wavefunction $W(x)$ such that $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$. In other words, $W(x)$ for the bound state is like a square root of probability. Furthermore, there is a $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In this note, we try to argue that $P(p)$, which is based on the measurement of momenta of particles knocked out of an ensemble of identical single particle bound states, does not have physical meaning within the bound state, unlike $P(p,x)$ which has physical meaning for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas both inside the gas and for particles released from a small hole in the gas wall. This forces one to create another function to "link" the two physically observed probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p)$.

Classical Statistical Mechanics (Maxwell-Boltzmann Situation)

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for a gas is given by:

$$P(p,x) = C \exp(-pp/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T) \text{ where } T \text{ is temperature and } V(x) \text{ potential } ((1))$$

The momentum portion of the ((1)) may be measured by making a small hole in the gas wall and noting the momenta of emitted particles. The spatial density may be measured within the gas.

There are various maximization of entropy approaches which may be used to derive ((1)), but we focus on the balance (of regular and time reversed) two-body reactions to obtain ((1)). At a point x , a two body collision may occur. One does not need to consider $V(x)$ at this point at first. Let $f(p)$ be the probability to find a particle with momentum p . Then, the probability for an elastic collision: $e_1 + e_2 \rightarrow e_3 + e_4$ where $e_i = p_i^2/2m$ is:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((2))$$

This ensures that every e_1 that combines with an e_2 to create an e_3 and e_4 will be replaced by a combining e_3 and e_4 . For an elastic reaction: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ so taking \ln of ((2)) and linking to conservation of energy yields $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. To bring $V(x)$ into the picture, one may note that $pp/2m + V(x_1) = p_2^2/2m + V(x_2)$ leading to ((1)).

The point we wish to make is the following. Given that physical two body reactions are occurring, one may ask what it means to have a particle with momentum p . Before colliding, the particle has momentum p , but as soon as it collides it changes to another momentum value. Thus, it is difficult to argue that the particle really has a momentum identity for more than a short time if many reactions are occurring. A statistical identity of a particle with momentum p , however, arises because on average as one particle with p reacts and is "lost" another is created keeping $f(p)$ constant in time.

Thus, the idea of $f(p)$, which is experimentally established by measuring particles which come out of a hole in the gas wall and no longer collide, also “makes sense” within the gas where collisions are occurring continuously. We argue that such is not the case in quantum mechanics.

Quantum Mechanics

For quantum bound states, one may measure $P(x)$ at each point x i.e. the spatial density just as in classical statistical mechanics. One may also take an ensemble of single particle bound states (all in the same state) and “knock” the particle out followed by a measurement of its momentum. This produces a probability density $\text{Probability}(p)=P(p)=b(p)$ of momenta which does not follow Newton’s law. Thus, it seems some kind of statistical mechanics may be at work. The question we ask is whether there is any notion of $P(p) = b(p)$ inside the bound system?

For the classical statistical gas, the concept of $P(p)$ holds both outside and within the gas because on average a disappearing particle with momentum p (due to a collision) is replaced by one created by a collision. There is a physical balance and so it makes sense to argue there is a certain probability $P(p)$.

In a quantum bound state, as a first step one does not think of Newton’s law, otherwise one has a classical system. One may then think of $V(x)$ rendering stochastic hits, but this is also classical. If one considers the single bound particle to have momentum p , its identity, just as in the classical statistical case, is mixed with that of a particle with momentum p_1 which gets a knock from $V(x)$ to move into momentum state p . For a one way reaction (just as in classical statistical mechanics), there is no balance and no identity of the particle with momentum p . For the classical statistical mechanical case, it is only through a balance with the time-reversed collision that this identity of p arises. For the quantum case, there is no such time-reversed balance. A particle with p has the identity p , but at the same time it may be interacting with $V(x)$ to become p_j . Thus, it has “multiple” identities and $P(p)$ does not seem to make sense within the bound state.

To see this in detail, consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$:

$$a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) + \text{Sum over } k \ V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

In ((2)), one may see the identity of a particle with momentum p in the first term on the LHS, while the second term shows that all other $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ momentum states share this p identity through an interaction with $V(x)$.

Thus, quantum mechanics differs statistically from classical statistical mechanics due to its lack of reaction balance defining $P(p)$ within the bound state. The consequence, it seems, is that one must introduce a new kind of probability, namely a conditional one to explain the experimental results $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ and link them:

$$b(p) = P(p) = \text{Integral } dx \ P(p/x) P(x) \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{Also: } P(x) = \text{Integral } dp \ P(x/p) P(p) \quad ((3b))$$

Thus, quantum mechanics leads to a completely new probability $P(p/x)$ which is not needed in classical statistical mechanics. Furthermore,

$$E - V(x) = \text{classical kinetic energy} = \sum_{\text{over } p} \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p/x) \quad ((4))$$

One may consider $P(p/x)$ having the following form:

$$P(p/x) = \frac{a(p) f(p,x)}{[\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) f(p,x)]} \quad ((5)) \text{ so it is normalized to 1.}$$

$$\text{Call } W(x) = [\sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) f(p,x)]$$

$a(p)$ is determined by the potential $V(x)$ i.e. different potential lead to different $a(p)$ sets.

Next, imagine that $f(p,x)$ forms an orthonormal set: Then:

$$P(p) = b(p) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p) \int \{P(x)/W(x)\} f(p,x) dx \quad ((6))$$

The integral yields a factor: $c(p)$. One sees from ((6)) that $P(x)/W(x)$ where $P(x)$ is spatial density is the important quantity within the bound state, not $P(x)$.

If one wishes to have a kind of symmetry between $P(p)$ and $P(x)$, a solution is:

$$P(x) = W(x)W(x) \text{ and } b(p) = a(p)a(p) \quad ((7))$$

This does not prove that ((7)) must be the solution, but the main point we wish to make is that even though $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ are physical observables, just as in classical statistical mechanics, due to a lack of time reversal balance the concept of $P(p)$ does not really hold within the bound state. Another probability function is needed and this leads to the idea of $P(p/x)$ and $W(x)$. Furthermore, if $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $W(x) = \sum_{\text{over } p} a(p)f(p,x)$, this leads to the idea of $f(p,x)$ being both positive and negative in order to ensure that $W(x)$ and $P(x)$ both go to zero in certain regions i.e. as $x \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ as in an oscillator problem. Thus, very different ideas from classical statistical mechanics emerge.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to examine why quantum mechanics, treated as a statistical theory, requires a wavefunction which is the "square root of $P(x)$ ". A single particle quantum state has measurable $P(x) = \text{spatial density}$ and $P(p)$ probabilities just like a classical statistical mechanical system. So why does it differ? We argue that $P(p)$, which measures the probability of momenta of particles knocked out of bound states, does not really have meaning within a bound system. The reason is that free particles are continuously interacting with the potential. Thus, one may have a free particle with momentum p , but at the same time it may interact with $V(x)$ and be converted into p_1 . In classical statistical mechanics, the same issue occurs. A particle with

momentum p may collide with another particle, but due to a balance with the time reversed reaction as one p disappears, another is created so the concept of $P(p)$ is well-defined. In a quantum bound state it is not. Thus, we argue that a new probability is needed, namely $P(p/x) = a(p)f(p,x)/W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)f(p,x)$ and $f(p,x)$ are orthonormal. We have argued above that it is possible to have a symmetrical solution such that $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$. Thus, $W(x)$ becomes the important spatial quantum mechanical probability type function.